

Extensive literature research for *Amyelois transitella* global distribution and eco-physiological parameters

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Introduction

Climate suitability analysis allows risk assessors to identify regions where climate is likely to support the establishment of a pest (ISPM 11, 2013). This analysis is typically based on pest biology and/or distribution according to the different methodology/models available (Devorshak, 2012). An extensive literature research was performed in order to gather relevant information on the ecology, physiology and distribution of the pest *Amyelois transitella*, in the context of the EFSA pest risk assessment (SANTE.GI/as Ref. Ares(2021)1571048). Hereby follows the description of the methodology adopted to search in scientific databases. The chosen methodology allows clear and complete reproducibility of all steps and decisions taken.

Search in scientific databases

Searches were performed to identify relevant information on the ecology, physiology, and distribution of the pest *Amyelois transitella*. Table 1 shows the list of databases that were consulted. Results from the scientific databases were crosschecked and integrated (if needed) with records in the EPPO and CABI databases.

Table 1. List of databases consulted for the extensive literature search

Databases	Platforms
Web of Science Core Collection	Web of Science
Biosis	
CAB Abstracts	
Chinese Science Citation Database	
Current Content Connect	
FSTA – the food science resource	
Korean Journal Database	
Medline	
Russian Science Citation Index	
SciELO Citation Index	
Scopus	Scopus

A combination of the scientific and international common names of the pest, retrieved from CAB Thesaurus¹ and EPPO Global database² (shown in Table 2), was used to interrogate the bibliographic databases. No other keywords were used (e.g., “biology”, “physiology”, “temperature”, etc...) in order not to limit the retrieval of documents that could include information useful for the purposes of this search as secondary information, especially in the case of pest distribution.

Table 2: Scientific and common names found in the consulted databases

Source	Scientific names
EPPO, CAB Thesaurus	<i>Amyelois transitella</i>
CAB Thesaurus	<i>Myelois duplipunctella</i>
CAB Thesaurus	<i>Myelois notabilis</i>
CAB Thesaurus	<i>Myelois notatalis</i>
CAB Thesaurus	<i>Myelois solitella</i>
EPPO, CAB Thesaurus	<i>Myelois venipars</i>
EPPO, CAB Thesaurus	<i>Paramyelois transitella</i>
	Common names
EPPO, CAB Thesaurus	Navel orange worm
EPPO, CAB Thesaurus	Navel caterpillar
CAB Thesaurus	Navel orangeworm

Table 3 shows the query syntax used in Web of Science and Scopus platforms, the date of the search and the number of documents obtained.

Table 3: Research strings used for the bibliographic databases consulted

Platform	Set	Date of search	Query	Results
Web of Science	#1	02/08/2021	TS=("Amyelois transitella" OR "Myelois duplipunctella" OR "Myelois notabilis" OR "Myelois notatalis" OR "Myelois solitella" OR "Myelois venipars" OR "Paramyelois transitella" OR "A transitella" OR "M duplipunctella" OR "M notatalis" OR "M solitella" OR "M venipars" OR "P transitella" OR ("navel orange" NEAR/3 worm*) OR (navel NEAR/3 (caterpillar* OR orangeworm*))) All Databases excluding Data citation Index and Zoological Report	593
SCOPUS	#1	02/08/2021	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Amyelois transitella" OR "Myelois duplipunctella" OR "Myelois notabilis" OR "Myelois notatalis" OR "Myelois solitella" OR "Myelois venipars" OR "navel caterpillar*" OR "Paramyelois transitella" OR "A transitella" OR "M duplipunctella" OR "M notatalis" OR "M solitella" OR "M venipars" OR "P transitella" OR ("navel orange" W/3 worm*) OR (navel W/3 orangeworm*))	218

¹ <https://www.cabi.org/publishing-products/cab-thesaurus/>

² <https://gd.eppo.int/>

All the references were exported to the reference manager software EndNoteX9 (The EndNote Team, 2013) and checked for duplicates. References were then imported (as compressed Endnote library) in the software DistillerSR (Evidence Partners, 2021) and screened.

Document screening

Document screening followed a two-step approach. In both steps the documents were screened answering the question “*Is there any information on physiology, ecology, and distribution of the pest?*”.

The first step was based on titles and abstracts and the above question was applied to identify the presence of elements in the abstract and title indicating the potential availability of information on physiology, ecology, and distribution of the pest in the full text. In case of positive answer, the type of information potentially available was specified (i.e., Physiology/Ecology, Distribution, or Other) (see Figure 1 as an example).

The screenshot displays the DistillerSR interface. On the left, a vertical sidebar contains the text "Quick Navigation" and "Log out". The main content area is divided into two sections. The top section, titled "Reference Details", shows the following information: "RefID: 22, Thermal-death kinetics of fifth-instar *Amyelois transitella* (Walker) (Lepidoptera : Pyralidae)", "Wang, S., Tang, J., Johnson, J. A., Hansen, J. D.", and "Attachments (Standard Version) | (Annotatable Version)". Below this is a "Reference Labels:" field containing "Web of Science". The bottom section contains the abstract text: "Information on kinetics for thermal mortality of navel orangeworm, *Amyelois transitella* (Walker) (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae), is needed for developing post-harvest phytosanitation thermal treatments of walnuts. Thermal-death kinetics for fifth-instar navel orangeworms were determined at temperatures between 46degreesC and 54degreesC at a heating rate of 18degreesC min(-1) using a heating block system. Thermal-death curves for fifth-instar navel orangeworms followed a 0.3th-order of kinetic reaction. The time required to achieve 100% mortality (N=0 = 600) decreased with increasing temperature in a logarithmic manner. Complete kill of 600 insects required a minimum exposure time of 140, 50, 15, 6, and 1 min at 46degreesC, 48degreesC, 50degreesC, 52degreesC, and 54degreesC, respectively. The reaction rate (k) was affected by treatment temperatures following an Arrhenius relationship. The activation energy for thermal kill of fifth-instar navel orangeworms was estimated to be between 510 and 520 kJ mol(-1). (C) 2002 Elsevier Science Ltd. All rights reserved." To the right of the abstract is a form with a "Submit Form" button and a dropdown menu set to "This Form - Next Reference". Below the form are two questions: "1. Is there any information on physiology, ecology and distribution of the pest?" with "Yes", "No", and "Unclear" buttons; and "2. Specify what type of information" with "Physiology/Ecology", "Distribution", "Others", and an empty text input field. At the top right of the form area are icons for "or Skip to Next" (trash and print icons).

Figure 1: Title and Abstract Screening, Screenshot from DistillerSR (DistillerSR. Version 2.35. Evidence Partners; 2021. Accessed August-September 2021. <https://www.evidencepartners.com>.)

Selecting the answer “yes”, the reference was automatically moved to the next level screening (full text). When it was unclear whether information of interest was available from the title and the abstract the answer “unclear” was selected, automatically carrying the paper on to the next step.

The second step of the screening was based on the full text analysis of the documents selected in the first step using the question stated above (see Figure 2 as an example).

RefID: 22, Thermal-death kinetics of fifth-instar *Amyelois transitella* (Walker) (Lepidoptera : Pyralidae)
 Wang, S.,Tang, J.,Johnson, J. A.,Hansen, J. D. Actions

Attachments
 PDF - 22-2002-Wang.pdf (Standard Version) | (Annotatable Version)

Reference Label(s):

Information on kinetics for thermal mortality of navel orangeworm, *Amyelois transitella* (Walker) (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae), is needed for developing post-harvest phytosanitation thermal treatments of walnuts. Thermal-death kinetics for fifth-instar navel orangeworms were determined at temperatures between 46degreesC and 54degreesC at a heating rate of 18degreesC min(-1) using a heating block system. Thermal-death curves for fifth-instar navel orangeworms followed a 0.5th-order of kinetic reaction. The time required to achieve 100% mortality (N=0 = 600) decreased with increasing temperature in a logarithmic manner. Complete kill of 600 insects required a minimum exposure time of 140, 50, 15, 6, and 1 min at 46degreesC, 48degreesC, 50degreesC, 52degreesC, and 54degreesC, respectively. The reaction rate (k) was affected by treatment temperatures following an Arrhenius relationship. The activation energy for thermal kill of fifth-instar navel orangeworms was estimated to be between 510 and 520 kJ mol(-1). (C) 2002 Elsevier Science Ltd. All rights reserved.

and go to or Skip to Next

1. INHERITED FROM TIAB SCREENING
Selection criteria in tiab

2. Is there any information on physiology, ecology and distribution of the pest?

3. What type of information

Figure 2: Full-text Screening, Screenshot from DistillerSR (DistillerSR. Version 2.35. Evidence Partners; 2021. Accessed August-September 2021. <https://www.evidencepartners.com/>.)

Data extraction

Data extraction was performed for the documents passing the full-text screening.

Data were extracted and reported in two files:

- One describing all the relevant information extracted, hereafter referred to as master file (ANNEX A, Master file .xlsx)
- the other including data on pest distribution (ANNEX B, Observation table .csv)

Table 4 shows the information extracted from the documents and collected in the master file.

Table 4: Information extracted from the documents and collected in the master file

Field name	Description	Type
Refid	Record ID. The Refid number is a unique number associated to each reference in Distiller	Integer
Reference	Full reference for the record	String
Source	Source of info	String
Abstract	Abstract or summary of the related document	String
Physiology_Ecology	Presence of information on physiology and/or ecology (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
Distribution	Presence of information on distribution (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
Other	Presence of additional information that could be of interest. Empty means no information	Boolean
T	Presence of information on temperature (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
RH	Presence of information on relative humidity or moisture (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
Photoperiod	Presence of information on photoperiod (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean

The distribution file collects data on the geographical observations of the pests (Table 5). To support a more detailed analysis of climate suitability, an effort was also done to categorize, when possible, the observations based on the organism status. Hence, two classifications for the pest status were created. The first one (Species_status1) based on the reported harmfulness of the organism (i.e. Pest, Non-Pest, Unclear) the second (Species_status2) based on the reported persistence of the organism in the area of observation (i.e. Persistent, Transient, or Unclear).

Table 5: *Amyelois transitella* observations extracted from the documents and collected in the distribution file.

Field name	Description	Type
Obs_ID	The Obs_ID is a unique number associated to each collected observation	Integer
Continent	Continent where the organism observation was reported	String
Country	Country where the organism observation was reported	String
State	State where the organism observation was reported	String
Observation	Location of the organism observation as reported in literature	String
Admin.level	FAO GAUL Administrative level of the observation ('location' in the case of specific geographic point)	Integer
Admin.source	Administrative shapefile layer used to identify the area of the organism observation (usually FAO GAUL layer)	String
Admin.code	FAO GAUL Administrative code of the observation ('NA' in the case of specific geographic point)	Integer
Lat	Latitude of the organism observation in decimal degrees	Double
Long	Longitude of the organism observation in decimal degrees	Double
Google_Earth_Coord	Indicates if Google Earth was used to identify the organism location. Google Earth coordinates were used only if the observation was not available in the FAO GAUL Administrative subdivision and in case of relatively small entities like towns/cities/provinces. Empty means that the coordinates were already indicated in the literature or that the location is identified by an administrative layer	Boolean
RefID	Record ID. The Refid number is a unique number associated to each reference in Distiller. This is the same field used also in Table 4.	Integer
Source.class	Classifies the source type (Scientific, Other)	String
Species_status1	Classifies the organism harmfulness in the area of observation (i.e. Pest, Non-Pest, Unclear)	String
Species_status2	Classifies the organism persistence in the area of observation (i.e. Persistent, Transient, or Unclear)	String
Uncertain	Flagged records (with 'x') refer to documents including uncertain information regarding the organism observation (e.g. records from museums, interceptions, not clear information)	Boolean

Results

The process followed to identify, screen and include eligible information on the ecology, physiology and distribution of the pest *Amyelois transitella* is summarized in the PRISMA diagram (Moher et al., 2009) in Figure 3. A total of 811 documents were retrieved from the search in scientific databases as described in Table 3. Overall, 593 documents were found through the Web of Science platform and 218 through the SCOPUS platform. Six additional references including information on physiology and distribution, found while gathering generic information on the pest in the very first stages of the study, were also added. After excluding duplicates, 771 documents were assessed for the first level screening (title and abstract). Out of these, 191 documents were selected for the second level screening (full text). A total of 97 papers were used for the data extraction from scientific databases out of which 69 included information on *A. transitella* distribution and 51 information on its ecophysiology. A report by Biosecurity Queensland (Biosecurity Queensland, 2012) also included information on the absence of the pest in the Australian territory based on a surveillance program.

The search on scientific databases was completed on 15th September 2021.

PRISMA 2009 Flow Diagram

Figure 3: PRISMA Diagram describing the process followed to identify, screen and include eligible information on the ecology, physiology and distribution of the pest *Amyelois transitella*.

References

- Biosecurity Queensland (Department of Employment, Economic Development and Innovation Biosecurity Queensland), 2012. Navel orangeworm. Have you seen this citrus pest? .
- Devorshak C, 2012. Plant pest risk analysis: concepts and applications, Cabi.
- Evidence Partners, online. DistillerSR.Version 2.35. [Accessed: August-September 2021].
- European Food Safety Authority; Application of systematic review methodology to food and feed safety assessments to support decision making. EFSA Journal 2010; 8(6):1637. [90 pp.]. doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2010.1637. Available online: www.efsa.europa.eu
- ISPM 11. 2013. Pest risk analysis for quarantine pests. Rome, IPPC, FAO. www.ippc.int
- Moher D, Liberati A, Tetzlaff J and Altman DG, 2009. Preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses: the PRISMA statement. BMJ, 339:b2535. doi: 10.1136/bmj.b2535
- The EndNote Team, 2013. EndNote. EndNote X9 Edition. Place Clarivate, Clarivate.